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DESIGN PROCESS FOR SUSTAINABILITY

THE IMPLICATIONS OF USER OBSERVATIONS FOR EMERGING POST-USE PRODUCT DESIGN SOLUTIONS

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ABSTRACT

Post-use design thinking is an approach for sustainability which enables a product to be reused in a new context after completing its initial use. People tend to re-use objects intuitively when they find the potential to re-contextualize them regardless of designer's intention. If a designer proposes an object for re-use, she/he should also be aware of the local knowledge in terms of people's needs, experiences and preferences related to post-use behaviours. Post-use design solutions would be well accepted and implemented if the user knowledge informs the early stages of product design and development process. This study aims to explore how the user observations inform the post-use dimensions and design solutions, and how that information is incorporated into the idea generation phase of the design process. To investigate this further, an undergraduate design project with an emphasis on post-use design thinking has been selected as the scope of this study.

Keywords: sustainability, user observations, post-use, idea generation, product design and development process.

INTRODUCTION

In response to current unsustainable practices of industrial production such as externalizing environmental and social impacts of product design, production, and use and disposal, alternative means are required that help bring together mass-production and local production for incorporating local tacit knowledge and skills, and enabling post-use services at the local batch-production scale for product repair, reuse and recovery (Walker, 2010; Fuad Luke, 2009; Dogan, 2007). These alternative

practices should be based on a more empowering system rather than recurring existing one, and should be built on a new way of design thinking that integrates sustainability knowledge into the early stages of the design process (Walker, Dogan and Marchand 2009). Additionally, the user knowledge should be incorporated into the idea generation phase of sustainable solutions, otherwise the gap between users and designers would occur, which would result in unsustainable consumption patterns such as unintended use, unacceptability of sustainable solutions and so on. The more profound knowledge about people's needs, experiences, preferences and expectations the designer gets; the more acceptable and adaptable sustainable solutions would emerge through design-based approaches.

This paper particularly emphasises the early stages (i.e. user observations and idea generation phases) of a third year industrial design studio project at the Middle East Technical University (METU), which aims to integrate post-use design considerations into the product design process. The paper presents initial conclusions for and insights into student projects with a focus on glass packaging solutions with double life to illustrate the implications of the user observations for encouraging and integrating post-use design solutions at the idea generation phase of the design process.

USER KNOWLEDGE AT THE IDEA GENERATION PHASE OF DESIGN

Knowledge emerged through both scientific and artistic processes within their epistemological and pedagogical framework has an effect on the design process. However, the design process is separated from both of them because of the uniqueness of

designers' behavioural and cognitive processes (Cross, 2006) in terms of the use of knowledge (Eder, 1966). In addition to the designers' latent knowledge, the research methods are used to elicit the knowledge to be incorporated into the design process through exploring and understanding the design context.

The design context involving physical, cognitive, social, cultural and emotional contexts (Kumar, 2009) cannot be considered separate from people. Understanding people's needs, behaviours, attitudes, and experiences is highly essential to explore the design context and to inform the design process. Designers create artefacts, products, services and systems for people (i.e. consumers, costumers, users), thus people should be an integral component of the design process (Mitchell, 1995; Hanington, 2007). Although the integration of people into the design process varies from being an observant to being an active participant according to different research methods (e.g. user observations, participatory techniques, etc.) in the design process, the user involvement aims to enrich and inform designers' knowledge about specific design tasks, and to expand designers' empathic horizon (McDonagh-Philp & Denton, 1999; Visser, et al., 2005; Suri & Howard, 2006; IDEO, 2009) through understanding the context of use, people's needs, and expectations. A better understanding of those associated with people's experiences in terms of time and environment would help designers avoid biases, since the designers tend to make assumptions about the users based on their own experiences and mental models. In the design process, designers may develop solutions through their projections about future uses and users through their experiences as users themselves, if the knowledge retrieved from user centered research is absent (Ornetzeder & Rohrer, 2006). When the mental gap between people and designers expands, design solutions might be used in an unintended way or might not be tailored to local needs and preferences.

The intention of this study is not to assess the acceptance of the design solutions but to illustrate how the user observations inform post-use design

considerations at the idea generation phase of the product design and development process.

METHODOLOGY

To have a better understanding of the local knowledge and context and to integrate post-use design considerations into the idea generation phase of design, a third-year industrial design project was developed and undertaken at the undergraduate level in the Department of Industrial Design, at METU in collaboration with a major glass packaging producer (i.e. Anadolu Cam A.S.).

The aim of this project was to develop design solutions presenting potentials of post-use design thinking in the area of glass packaging for food and beverages. The project focused on both the use and the post use phases of the product lifespan, which also emphasized on the transformation of mass-produced glass packaging into promotional products (i.e. water bottles, candle jars and bathroom accessories) through integrating locally produced parts and/or surface finishing applications. The phases of this project included literature search, user observations, idea generation exercises (divergence), preliminary jury (convergence), presenting design details and final design solutions.

The main goal of this study was to explore how user observations informed the post-use dimensions and design concepts, and how that information was incorporated into the idea generation phase of the design process. For this end, the implications of the user observations for the post-use design concepts were analysed and presented within the scope of this study.

During the user observations, the students visited several homes and they documented the types of glass packaging being re-used, various applications on glass packaging for re-use, and functional and decorative qualities of re-used products within their context.

Upon the completion of the user observations and the literature search phases, the students generated several design concepts through an idea generation exercise. This generative tool helped the students

develop diverse design concepts for both the use and the post-use phases. This exercise was the primary tool for the initial and emerging post-use design concepts. Each student developed at least three design concepts individually and three additional ones in group leading to over two hundred initial design solutions. For the aim of this study, design concepts developed by the students were firstly examined and then compared with the results and visual recordings from the user observation phase. After this analysis, ten out of 37 students were recruited for in-depth interviews, considering that at least one of the design concepts, which was developed by these selected students, were directly informed and influenced by the user observations. The exemplary cases presented here constitute a small portion of the whole design concepts for both the use and post-use phases developed by all 37 students (Table 2).

The data from the interviews were analyzed thoroughly concept by concept, and then were categorized considering the implications of the user observations and recordings for the design concepts in terms of post-use and re-use. Emerging definitions of dimensions for the post-use design concepts such as personalization, engaging, local, et cetera were retrieved from the responses of the participants, and how those dimensions informed the initial post-use concepts were analyzed.

Upon the completion of the in-depth interviews, an open-ended survey was conducted among the whole third-year design students via Internet. The responses of the students were analyzed considering the contribution of the user observations to the idea generation phase.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the findings and discussions of in-depth interviews and online survey consequently.

IN-DEPTH INTERVIEWS

During the in-depth interviews, to understand how the user observations inspired the idea generation phase and informed the post-use dimensions, the students were shown visual recordings from the user observations and were asked about

- the inspiring post-use examples gathered during the user observations,
- how each concept emerged during the idea generation phase and what the inspirations were,
- to what extent user observations informed and inspired the emerging design concepts.

According to the findings from the in-depth interviews, the design concepts were categorized as shown in the Table 1. During this analysis, it was found difficult to determine whether a design concept was completely inspired from the user observations or not. Visual recordings from the students' design concepts and user observations were pre-analyzed to understand to what extent the post-use examples inspired the initial design ideas. The students might also be inspired subconsciously by the user observations, and might not be aware of it and not reveal this during the interviews. This might have implications for limiting the number of the design concepts to be analysed and presented in this study. All of the sixteen design concepts in total were analysed and categorized below that either the students or the authors considered as being inspired by the user observations. Only exemplary cases for each category were presented in the Table 2 based on the analysis of the initial design concepts and the findings from the in-depth interviews.

The main emphasis of the user observations was on the post-use phase. For developing further projects in design education, it might also be useful to include and emphasize both the use and post-use phases in the user observations in order to encourage diverse design solutions and to better link the use and the post-use design solutions.

Categories		*Pre-analysis: matching the concept with the visual recordings	Number of concepts
A	The student stated that the concept was inspired by the user observations and the student matched it with users' post-use examples/solutions (i.e. visual recordings).	Matched	2
B	The student stated that the concept was inspired by the user observations and the student <u>did not</u> match it with users' post-use examples/solutions.	Matched	3
C	The student stated that the concept was inspired by the user observations and the student <u>did not</u> match it with users' post-use examples/solutions.	not matched	2
D	The student <u>did not</u> confirm that the concept was inspired by the user observations and visual recordings.	Matched	9

*Initial analysis supported the fact that the design concept was matched with the visual recordings from the user observations.

Table 1. Categorization of design concepts according to responses

Post-use dimensions for sustainability

Various post-use dimensions emerged through the user observations were retrieved from the students' responses. Those were personalization, affordability engaging and locally inspired solutions.

Personalization (8) is the most frequently mentioned dimension for the post-use design solutions. Each student assessed and incorporated this dimension differently with respect to the results from the user observations. For instance, *Student 2* defined personalization as 'allowing the user to apply

unlimited variations on glass packaging, while *Student 4* defined it as 'adding a personal value to the product to make it more diverse and attractive' (See Table 2). Engaging solutions (3) and affordability (3) were equally mentioned considering the students' responses. The notion of 'locally inspiring' was only mentioned by one student as an inspirational dimension for the post-use design concept. To enrich the students' understandings of the context and the use of post-use dimensions, it would be useful to gather, analyse and include more post-use examples from the user observations which would eventually lead to more inspiring and diverse design solutions.

Table 2 illustrates some of the post-use design concepts, and how the user observations (e.g. the users' post use examples) inspired and informed them. First column shows the category (See Table 1) in which the student belongs to. The second and third columns present the design concepts including their descriptions. The fourth column presents the visual recordings from the user observations informing the design solutions. Finally, the last column includes post-use dimensions emerged from the user observations. For instance, *Student 1* develops a pomegranate sauce bottle concept that turns into a candle stick during the post-use phase. The design concept is based on a conclusion drawn from the user observations considering people's intention to put something inside a product for decorative purposes during the post-use phase. Thus, the student defines personalization particularly in this design solution as 'allowing users to put various materials in the glass packaging'.

	Design concept	Post-use examples from user observations	Post-use dimensions
Student 1 (Category A)	<p>The user puts ornamental materials in the glass packaging for decorative purposes.</p>	<p>Personalization: Allowing users to put various materials in the glass packaging (e.g. jars and bottles)</p>	
Student 2 (Category A)	<p>The user personalizes the jar through covering it with knitting to make it a decorative object.</p>	<p>Personalization : Allowing users to make unlimited variations or changes on the glass packaging by applying hand-made pouches</p>	
Student 3 (Category B)	<p>Robes or strings with various colors, thicknesses and materials are available at users homes.</p>	<p>Engaging: Incorporating users into the post use phase by allowing them to use various robes or strings through wrapping them around the jar in order to create diverse light and shadow effects</p>	

Table 2. Selected post-use design concepts in terms of their relationship with user observations and post-use dimensions

	Design concept	Post-use examples from user observations	Post-use dimensions
Student 4 (Category C)	<p>Design concept by Buse Ustun Use: Milk bottle; Post-use: Water bottle Pictures and/or notes can be inserted into an accessory placed on the neck of the bottle and connected to the lid, which adds a personal value to the water bottle and makes it more attractive for potentials users.</p>	<p>Based on the findings from the observations, the user would add something to the glass packaging to reuse it after its initial use for personalization.</p>	<p>Personalization: Adding a personal value (e.g. photographs, memory, notes) to the glass packaging to make it more attractive for post-use</p>
Student 5 (Category D)	<p>Design concept by Sirin Cincioglu Use: Wine bottle; Post-use: Water bottle The design concept is inspired by water vessel shape and covered with straw based strings and/or robes for a water bottle sleeve holding both aesthetic and functional value.</p>	<p>The user incorporates locally available materials for decorative purposes for the post-use phase.</p>	<p>Locally inspired: Usage of locally available materials (e.g. straw) and resemblance of the form to the ancient water vessel shape</p>

Table 2. Selected post-use design concepts in terms of their relationship with user observations and post-use dimensions (cont.)

Based on the post-use examples from the user observations, it was concluded that these examples have a main emphasis on decorating the glass packaging products. However, the students re-contextualised these inspirational examples in terms of both aesthetic and functional values. For instance, a personalized decorative object was reconceptualised in a water bottle sleeve as the post-use design concept embodying both aesthetic and functional (i.e. non-slip grip and protection of the glass packaging) features developed by the *Student 2*. Similarly, decorative strings covering a water bottle inspired a post-use design accessory for a candle jar allowing potential users demonstrate their skills and creativity, and providing different patterns for light and shadow effects presented by the *Student 3*. Although the post-use examples from the user observations were based on mainly

aesthetic values, some students were able to reinterpret these to bring together both aesthetics and function (e.g. candle jar shade, water bottle sleeve, etc.).

ONLINE SURVEY

After the completion of the in-depth interviews, an online survey was sent to the whole third year industrial design students to better understand the contributions of the user observations at the idea generation phase of the project. The survey included two questions. The first question was about to what extent they benefited from the user observations for the idea generation phase, and the second one was about the implications of the user observations for the design concepts.

The number of students that replied the survey was 23 out of 37. The students mainly stated that the user observations helped them better understand the concept of 'post-use' and 're-contextualization'. This included the diverse post-use scenarios for glass packaging, problems and challenges encountered while transforming a glass packaging into another product, and people's needs, behaviours, expectations and intentions regarding post-use. Main findings are as below:

- People tend to collect the same glass packaging for post-use to make or complete a set (i.e. family of products).
- Aesthetic features of glass packaging are important for people to keep it for a prolong time. For instance, people might purchase a product considering the post-use of the glass packaging, if they find it aesthetically appealing.
- People prefer to transform glass packaging for post-use purposes through simple processes. Removing the label is a difficult phase while transforming a product for post-use.
- The post-use processes would be diversified based on user's gender, age and lifestyle. For instance, at student homes or in dormitories, bottles or jars are reused through making simple changes on glass packaging such as removing the label to basically store food. However, at domestic households, people tend to apply ornaments to personalize the glass packaging in a more complicated way through using their craft skills.
- People commonly prefer to add personal value to products for post-use purposes.

The findings and insights from the user observations expanded the students' vision on generating new ideas, and identified their constraints and limitations for the project. They also gathered a great amount of information related to post-use in a very limited time as they shared the findings of their research with the whole class.

The main limitation as stated by the student was that most of the examples from the user observations were on reusing glass packaging for storing food and beverages. During the observations

the students found out fewer examples for the project post-use categories such as candle jar, water bottle, bathroom accessories. Thus, the students analysed the current examples more thoroughly in order to transfer that knowledge into the proposed post-use categories considering people's needs, preferences and expectations.

CONCLUSION

The post-use design thinking is an evolving research area in design for sustainability which prolongs life spans of products by allowing enduring relationships between products and users. For this end, post-use considerations should be incorporated into the early stages of the design process, and those considerations should be informed by user knowledge to propose more locally relevant solutions for people.

In this study, the user observation method was presented to illustrate the findings on how the design research informed the post-use dimensions (e.g. personalization, locally inspired, engaging, affordability) and design concepts, and how that information from this exploratory research on post-use was integrated into the idea generation phase of design process. However, not only the user observations but also other design research methods that involve people in the design process would inspire and inform the design solutions for sustainability. People's involvement in the idea generation phase is critical in terms of product design for sustainability, since it is essential for designers to understand people's needs, preferences and expectations in order to bridge the gap between users and sustainable design solutions.

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